

LINGUISTIC SIMILARITIES AND DIFFERENCES BETWEEN STANDARD ENGLISH AND AMERICAN ENGLISH

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The main tasks of dialectology are to describe the structural variants of a language and to determine the boundaries between dialect regions or social stratifications. Like any language, English has internal variations, it consists of many variants and, in a certain sense, is the sum of these variants. As the English language is becoming more and more widespread around the world, its dialects are also increasing, and this, in turn, requires their study. Before we examine the similarities and differences between Standard English and the American variant, it will help to provide a coherent coverage of this topic by providing scientific theories and concepts about them.

There are many dialects and countless accents of English in Great Britain. Despite the relatively small area of the island, many forms of the language are spoken there. This diversity of dialects and accents allows for different uses of the language and serves as an important means of expressing the social class of individuals. It is for this reason that, from a linguistic point of view, there is sometimes a spirit of competition or stereotyping; this leads to discrimination by speakers of the main dialects against representatives of regional dialects. However, in linguistics, if a group uses a language in a distinctive way and if this use is subject to certain rules, then such speech is valued as a dialect. Therefore, regardless of social status, whether standard or non-standard, all dialects existing in the United Kingdom are worth studying from a linguistic point of view. [English Live. *British Accents and Dialects: A Rough Guide*. EF English Live.].

Standard English or British English (BE) is the version of English spoken in the British Isles (England, Scotland, Wales and Ireland) and its former colonies (e.g. Australia, India, Canada). It is based mainly on British culture, education, literature and history. Standard English (SE) is the dialect used mainly in written speech and spoken by the country's most intelligent people. In fact, in England there is an accent or concept associated with this Standard English, which is called "Received Pronunciation" (RP) (where the word "received" means "accepted").

Because of its historical and social roots, Standard English and Received Pronunciation are closely related to the language of the middle and upper classes of English society, and are often referred to as "Queen's English" or "BBC English". According to the English linguist P. Trudgill, "Received Pronunciation" is the pronunciation of Standard English, which is spoken by only 12–15% of the population, of whom about 7–12% use the RP accent mixed with regional accents such as Scouse or Geordie. Standard English is defined primarily by its grammar, vocabulary, and spelling [2. 1679 p.].

From a historical perspective, the dialect that is now known as “Standard English” is the result of a long period of change that began in the Middle Ages and was influenced by social, political, cultural, and economic factors. In fact, after the English court was moved from Winchester to London in the 15th century, the formation of the current Standard English language was closely linked to the historical development of the capital. The form of the language spoken in London and the East Midlands became established as the standard English of the court and gradually became the standard used in the fields of law, government, literature, and education in Britain.

Based on the above, the relationship between the dialects of British English and the accepted standard pronunciation is a means of reflecting the purely social stratification of the language. The formation of the standard language is the result of historical and political factors (the transformation of London into the capital), and it can be said that today it is mainly the norm of written speech and official communication.

There is considerable disagreement among linguists about whether Standard English can be classified as a dialect. Some scholars believe that Standard English is distinguished from other dialects in a number of ways, in particular by the presence of its own writing system. They argue that dialects and their study should focus primarily on spoken language, i.e., spoken language, and that the written form should be neglected. However, this approach can be controversial, as it ignores the fact that many non-standard English dialects in England—such as the Black Country dialect of the West Midlands or the Geordie dialect of North East England—have their own written traditions. [3. 240 p.].

Thus, other linguists, such as Trudgill and Chambers, consider Standard English to be a dialect. They argue that everyone speaks at least one dialect and that Standard English is a dialect, just like other forms of English. Although the term American English (AE) generally refers to the English spoken in the United States, the term also refers to the differences between American and other Englishes. In fact, American English is a product of British colonialism and is believed to have a historical-linguistic basis.

Today, there are several dialects of English in America. Therefore, dialectologists classify dialect regions in the United States in different ways: some are based on pronunciation, others on lexical or grammatical differences. Nevertheless, there are traditional main dialect regions in the United States, which in turn include many subdialects and sociolects. General American English (GenAm) is close to the most standard variant, spread mainly in the Midwest, but we have considered that it is found in almost all regions of the United States.

Regional dialects in the United States reflect the linguistic elements of the major immigrant groups in each region, especially in terms of pronunciation and vocabulary. There are four main regional varieties of English spoken in the United States: Northern (Northeastern), Southern, Midland, and Western. [7. 596 p].

General American (GA or GenAm) is a system of accents common among the population of the United States, which does not have a single standard accent, but rather several closely related accents. The General American accent is usually used to refer to the speech of Americans who do not have a distinct Eastern or Southern accent, that is, are devoid of regional, ethnic, or socioeconomic characteristics. The term was first popularized in 1925 by the American linguist GP Krapp. In 1982, the British phonetician JC Wells noted that two-thirds of Americans speak with a General American accent. [8. 524 p.].

The General American accent is now widely used, especially in the media. Because this accent has a generalized and neutral pronunciation, it is used by the media. For this reason, it is sometimes called "Network English" or "Network Standard". This accent has a relatively uniform and "colorless" appearance and is widespread throughout the United States. [9. 664 p.].

The main phonological features of Standard American pronunciation are:

- *Rhoticity:* One of the most important phonological characteristics of the General American accent is rhoticity. That is, the /r/ sound is pronounced clearly, even at the end of a word or after a vowel (e.g. curt, far, cart).
- *Glottalization (Glottalization of the /t/ sound):* The /t/ sound before the syllabic [n] is pronounced as a glottal stop (e.g., button ['bʌʔn]).
- *Intervocal flapping:* This feature causes the consonants /t/ and /d/ to be pronounced as [ɾ] (alveolar flap) between vowels or liquid consonants (e.g., water ['wɔːɾə], party ['pɑːɾi], model ['mɑːɾ]).
- *Yod-dropping (the phenomenon of dropping the /j/ consonant in some words, especially before vowels):* This phenomenon is associated with the dropping of the /j/ sound, especially after alveolar consonants (for example, the absence of the /j/ sound in the word new).

In general, the General American accent is considered the most neutral and standard pronunciation system in the United States, which differs from many regional and social accents and is widely used in the media. Although the United States and Great Britain speak the same language, their cultures are not completely compatible, and several variants of the English language have developed in both countries. These variants are explained by differences in spelling, pronunciation, accent, and vocabulary. Although English originated in England, it has been widely used in the Americas since its discovery. Due to the large number of English immigrants to the New World, English has become the main language in America.

However, today, as a result of media, technology, and the global influence of the United States, American English has become standardized and has even begun to influence British English. As a result, many American terms have supplanted British terms (for example, the use of the word radio instead of wireless, the widespread use of the word okay). Also, the active use of the following word-forming suffixes in American English is an example of this [10. 769 p.].

The main differences between Standard and American English from the following aspects:

- *Phonological:* In American English, the "r" sound is usually pronounced clearly (rhotic), while in British English it is often not pronounced (non-rhotic).
- *Spelling:* American English tends to be simpler and shorter, dropping unnecessary letters or making them closer to the pronunciation. British spelling often retains historical forms, such as "color" instead of "colour" in American English. "center" instead of "centre", It is written as "realize" instead of "realise".
- *Vocabulary and word choice:* American English (AmE) and British English (BrE) use different words to describe the same denotation (object, reality). In linguistics, this phenomenon is called dialectal vocabulary difference, for example, "elevator" in American English and "lift" in British English; "holiday" instead of "vacation"; "lorry" is used instead of "truck"
- *Syntax and morphology:* American and British English are characterized by morphological and syntactic differences, historical evolution (got/gotten), and regional standardization of grammatical agreement (singular/plural with collective nouns): American

English uses the form "gotten" while British English uses "got"; with collective nouns, a singular verb may be used in American English, while a plural verb may be used in British English.

Swan explains the most important common difference between American and British English speech as follows: some words are pronounced with the sound /u:/ in American English, while in British English they are pronounced with the sound /ju:/. Such words are usually words that have the letters d, t, n (sometimes s or l) followed by the letters u or ew ¹. For example: The word *Enthusiastic* is pronounced /in. θ u:ziæstɪk/ in American English, while in British English it is pronounced /in. θ ju:ziæstɪk/. The word *tune* is pronounced /tu:n/ in American English, and /tju:n/ in British English, The word *new* is pronounced /nu:/ in American English, and /nju:/ in British English, The word *illuminate* is pronounced /ilu:mineɪt/ in American English and /ɪlju:mineɪt/ in British English.

British English has one additional vowel sound compared to American English. This vowel sound is the round short /ɒ/, which is used in words such as "cot", "dog", "got", "off", "stop", "lost". In American English, these words are usually pronounced with /ɑ:/ (for example, as the first vowel in the word "father") or /ɒ:/ (for example, as the first vowel in the word "caught"). It is worth noting that this vowel sound is also pronounced differently in British and American English.

Some words, such as "fast", which are spelled with the letter "a" and a consonant, have different pronunciations: in standard southern British English they are pronounced with the sound /ɑ:/, and in American English and some other varieties of English they are pronounced with the sound /æ/.

In many varieties of American English, the letters "t" and "d" become a very soft, voiced /d/ sound between vowels. For example, the words "writer" and "rider" can be pronounced the same. In British English, however, these two words are clearly distinguished: /raɪtə(r)/ and /raɪdə(r)/.

Some long words, especially those ending in "-ary", "-ery" or "-ory", are pronounced with one syllable more in American English than in British English. For example, the word "secretary" is pronounced /'sekɹətəri/ in American English, but /'sekɹətɹi/ in British English.

The stress position in words borrowed from French often varies, especially if the word ends in a vowel. In American English, the final vowel of such words is usually pronounced with stress, while in British English, this sound is unstressed.

Pate - /pæ'teɪ/ (AmE) - /'pæteɪ/ (BE)

Ballet /bæ'leɪ/ (AmE) - /'bæleɪ/ (BE)

Spelling differences.

Baugh American English spelling often differs slightly from that adopted in England. These differences are sometimes not noticeable, as some British spellings are still used in America, and some American innovations are now accepted in both countries. Noah Webster played a major role in introducing spelling innovations into American English. Baugh (ibid.) notes that most of the spellings peculiar to American English were popularized by Webster's initiative and inclusion in his dictionary [12. P. 429.].

Most two-syllable words and some longer words are spelled with the "-ise" form in both British and American English. The following words have no spelling differences and use the "-

¹ Swan, M. *Practical English Usage*. – 3rd ed. – Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2005.p43-44

ise" suffix in both languages: *surprise* (not "surprize" in American English), *despise*, *supervise*, *revise*, *compromise*, *televise*, *advise*, *exercise*, *advertise*, *comprise*, *improvise*, etc.

In the next section, we will give a few more examples of spelling differences:

- *axe* (British English) - *ax* (American English)
- *plough* (British English) - *plow* (American English)
- *tyre* (British English) - *dash* (American English)

And below, we can cite as examples some of the spelling differences that occur when switching from British English to American English:

- Dropping the letter "u": for example, "colour" – "color"; "honor" - "honor".
- shortening two letters instead of one: "waggon" – "wagon"; "traveler" - "traveler"; "program" - "program"; "kilogramme" - "kilogram".
- In words ending in "-re", swap the last two letters: "centre" - "center"; "theatre" - "theater"; "metre" - "meter".
- Abbreviations of words are also characteristic: "cheque" – "check"; "catalogue" – "catalog"; as well as informal forms "through" – "thru", "high" – "hi", "low" – "lo".
- Replacing the letter "x" with "ct": "inflexion" – "inflection"; "connexion" – "connection".
- Use the letters "s" instead of "c" and "z" instead of "s" to match the pronunciation: "licence" – "license"; "offence" – "offense"; "paralyse" – "paralyze".

Differences in lexical (word usage)

Baugh notes that the differences in vocabulary and idioms in American English are a widely discussed topic. In fact, English has retained some words that were used in America in the 17th century, while these words are obsolete and no longer used in British English. Americans have been defending the form of English that has existed since the 16th century. At the same time, many words that were preserved in British English have disappeared from American English. For example, the word "waistcoat" is used as a name for clothing in British English, while in American English it is called "vest"; "vest" usually means "undershirt" in Britain.

Some topographical words in British English are also not used in America: for example, words such as "fen", "spinney", "copse", and "heath" are not found in American English.

Some words can be used in both versions of English, but their frequency of use differs and other words are used instead in the other version. For example, "flat" and The word "apartment" exists in both American and British English, with the word "flat" being preferred in Britain, while "apartment" is preferred in America. is used more often. Another example is the words "shop" and "store", as well as "post" and "mail".

In conclusion, the development of American English from the 1920s to the present can be seen as a period closely linked to mass media, immigration, social equality movements, and digital technologies. During this period, two trends in the language occurred simultaneously - standardization and diversification. Modern linguistic technologies, corpora, and mediatization make it possible to analyze changes in the language in real time.

The stages of development of American English and the classification of dialects are considered as a whole, it becomes clear that the process of language formation is complex, multi-layered and closely related to historical and social factors. Since the colonial period, various regional variants of English have gradually mixed, gradually forming a new language system of its own. In the years of independence, the language became a symbol of national

identity and began to develop independently of British English. In later periods, because of the industrial revolution, large-scale migration of the population, urbanization and international relations, new dialect areas were formed, which did their lexical, phonetic and grammatical features distinguish. Although American English has become one of the most influential languages globally, it is not monolithic, but consists of regional and social diversity. While Northern, Southern, Midland, Western, Appalachian, New York, and Coastal New England dialects represent regional identities, sociolects such as AAVE and Chicano English have become important indicators of ethnic and social identity. At the same time, neutral accents such as General American have become widespread as national and international norms, replacing traditional local features among the younger generation.

Thus, the media, especially television, cinema, radio and social networks, play a decisive role in the popularization and spread of dialects, unifying the language on the one hand and on the other hand, creating opportunities for different dialects and sociolects to be recognized at the national level. This process of language development shows that American English is not only a means of communication, but also an important mirror of cultural heritage and social identity. Therefore, in dialectological research, it is considered a scientific novelty to study it not only from a linguistic, but also from a sociological, historical and cultural perspective

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